

A STUDY ON SELF-ESTEEM OF URBAN AND RURAL LIVING TRANSGENDER IN WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT:

Transgender individuals often face a variety of challenges, especially in relation to social adjustment and isolation. Due to their gender identity, they often experience a lack of family support and are subjected to social exclusion. Transgender individuals are at an increased risk for various mental and physical health problems, substance abuse, and suicide. This study focuses on the self-esteem of urban and rural transgender in West Bengal. Total number of samples was 70 and divided into 2 parts from urban living and rural living transgender in West Bengal. The Rosenberg self-esteem scale (RSES) was used as the tool for data collection. The test found that the self-esteem of urban living areas was $M = 17.86$, $SD = 4.53$, and self-esteem of rural living areas, it was $M = 14.77$, $SD = 4.54$. The results show that transgender people living in urban areas have normal self-esteem. Transgender people living in rural areas have low self-esteem.

KEYWORDS:

SELF-ESTEEM, URBAN LIVING, RURAL LIVING, TRANSGENDER AND WEST BENGAL.

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TRANSGENDER

A person who does not accept their biological sex assigned at birth is referred to by various terms such as transgender, trans man, trans woman, or gender queer. Transgender people have been a part of Indian society for centuries. Various cultures are found in India, and according to these cultural distinctions, people in India refer to them by different names, such as Hijra, Aravani, Shiva Shakti, Joggapa, etc. These communities are mentioned in centuries-old texts, such as the Vedas and Puranas, reflecting the inclusiveness and recognition of their existence. Vedic and Puranic literature mentions the terms *Tritiya Prakriti*, meaning 'third sex', and *Napumsaka*, meaning 'impotent' or 'without fertility'—concepts that are integral to the texts and philosophy of ancient India. The term 'hijra' in the Indian context is believed to originate from Persian. The word 'hijra' is derived from the Persian word 'hiz,' which can refer to someone who is effeminate or perceived as ineffective or incompetent.

Nowadays, many transgender people are often seen begging at traffic signals, working as sex workers, or performing at weddings. This reflects their constant struggle for social acceptance and economic opportunities. However, during the Mughal period, eunuchs known as 'khawajasaras' enjoyed respected and influential positions. They served as guards, administrators, and advisors in the royal court. The term 'hijra' is derived from the Greek word 'euneukhos,' literally meaning 'bedroom attendant.'

This reflects their traditional role as guardians of the royal harem in many ancient societies, as they were considered impotent and unable to reproduce. During British rule, eunuchs were systematically marginalized. Colonial laws criminalized their existence and activities, depriving them of the civil rights and respected status they once enjoyed. The British colonial administration classified eunuchs as a separate caste or tribe, often associating them with criminal activities such as kidnapping, sterilizing children, and performing in public while dressed as women.

The Supreme Court of India's April 2014 judgment in the case of National Legal Services Authority (NALSA) vs. Union of India was a landmark decision for the rights of transgender individuals. The Court recognized transgender people as a third gender, affirming that sexual orientation and gender identity are fundamental aspects of the right to life, dignity, and freedom under the Constitution of India. Following the landmark NALSA judgment in 2014, several legislative efforts were made to formalize and expand the rights of transgender individuals in India. The Rights of Transgender Persons Bill, 2014, introduced in the Rajya Sabha, aimed to implement the directives of the NALSA judgment. The Rights of Transgender Persons Bill, 2015, introduced by the government, made significant modifications to the 2014 bill. It removed provisions related to the Transgender Rights Court and the National and State Commissions,

which was seen as a dilution of the initial efforts to protect transgender rights.

SELF -ESTEEM

In psychology, self-esteem is used to define a person’s sense of their own personal value. In other terms, self-esteem can be described as how much an individual perceives themselves in various situations. Self-esteem is our firm belief and confidence in ourselves. An individual’s self-esteem is usually defined by factors such as feelings of security, personality, sense of belonging, how others react to us, and our thoughts, among others. The beliefs that people have about themselves determine who they are as individuals, what their roles and purposes in life are, and what they can achieve. These strong inner impacts provide internal mechanisms that help in guiding life choices and monitoring one’s behavior. Self-esteem can also be referred to as self-regard and self-worth.

Self-esteem can also be described as the perception of self-regard, or the extent to which a person values, prizes, or admires themselves. Self-esteem can primarily be described as the overall judgment of oneself in either a positive or negative way. It indicates the extent to which a person believes themselves to be competent and worthy of living. The construct of self-esteem is recognized today as a major factor in learning outcomes. Self-esteem is a socio-psychological construct that assesses an individual’s attitudes and perceptions of self-worth. Thus, self-esteem is an understanding of one’s quality as an individual—that is, how good or bad, valuable or worthless, positive or negative, or superior or inferior one is. Individual assessments of self-esteem are formed through two interrelated processes. First, individuals compare their social identities, opinions, and abilities with others. To the extent that individuals feel inferior to those with whom they interact, their self-esteem will be negatively affected. Second, individuals assess themselves through their interactions with others. People learn to see themselves as others believe them to be.

The term ‘self-esteem’ is used to describe a person’s overall sense of self-worth or personal value. Self-esteem is often seen as a personality trait, which means that it tends to be stable and enduring. Self-esteem can involve a variety of beliefs about the self, such as the appraisal of one’s own appearance, beliefs, emotions, and behaviors (Branden, N. 1969). Factors contributing to mental health are an understudied area of transgender health. Meyer’s model of minority stress (Meyer et al., 2008) proposes that experiences of stigma, such as discrimination

OBJECTIVE

- To study the self-esteem of rural living transgender.
- To study the self -esteem of urban living transgender.
- To study the self- esteem of West Bengal transgender.
- To study the self- esteem of transgender.

REVIEW LITERATURE

Nair P. & Gosh S. (2022) in their study to find out the Self-Esteem of Young Adults in 30 male and 30 female age range 20 – 30. The result shown that the male and female group have high self-esteem. But according to comparison between male and female it has observed that female have high self-esteem then male.

Shrivastava N, Agarwal S, in their study on self-esteem among young adult in Lucknow Universities on 120 male and female, and the results of the study revealed that male had good self-esteem than female. It was also found that there was a non-significant difference between gender and self-esteem which meant that self-esteem was not dependent or influenced by gender.

Rayan, Watsan, Arnold H. Grossman and Stephen (2012) in this study social support theory is used as a frame work to analyse data from the sample of 835 LGB Youth. It studies the support from close friends, Teachers, class mates and parents. All support is importance to the participants and it was closely related to higher self-esteem and lower level of depression. This study also measures both the importance and presence of the social support for LGB youth.

METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted in West Bengal. Transgenders were selected from different places like NGOs, Traffic signals, Toll Plaza and many more from urban and rural living area. The sample of 70 urban and rural living transgender were studies. Sample of 70 transgender will be selected by random sampling method. Sample will be taken into 2 equal part, 35 transgenders from urban and 35 transgenders from rural living.

To collect the data, I visited many places like NGOs, sex workers' places, transgender' homes, their working places and many more. They all live in different places according to their work under their Guru Maa. In the present study, we have divided 70 data into 2 parts, 35 data for rural living transgender and 35 data for urban living transgender.

TABLE 1: SELF -ESTEEM OF URBAN LIVING AND RURAL LIVING TRANSGENDER

Urban Living Transgender	Rural Living Transgender	Total No of Transgender
35	35	70

RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF STUDY

The result and discussion of rural living and urban living Transgender’s self-esteem.

TABLE 2: SHOW THE SELF ESTEEM OF URBAN LIVING AND RURAL LIVING TRANSGENDER

Transgender Living Area	Mean	SD	Level Of Self Esteem
Urban Living	17.86	4.53	Normal Self-Esteem

Rural Living	14.77	4.54	Low Self-Esteem
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The purpose of this research was to study of self-esteem of urban living and rural living transgender. The overall sample (N=70), the participant ages ranged between 20 to 60. In table 1 its shows the transgender divided into 2 parts 35 urban living and 35 rural living. In table 2 the study on self-esteem in urban living Mean =17.86, SD= 4.53 and self- esteem of rural living Mean =14.77, SD= 4.54. The result shows that the transgender living in urban area their self-esteem is normal also Transgender living in rural area their self-esteem is low.

CONCLUSION

Every person is special and their self-esteem is very important. Self-esteem is linked with everyone value and aim. If we support transgender people to improving their self-esteem so it can lead to increased happiness and positivity. The result found that the low self-esteem in rural living area transgender. Self-esteem is critical factor influencing their cognitive and emotional responses. The role of self-esteem in potentially reducing suicide rates among transgender individuals. The finding says urban living area transgender self-esteem is normal. Transgender living in rural area they suffer more than transgender living in urban area. Transgender living in urban area they are getting more opportunities but in rural living transgender not getting proper opportunities. The NGOs working very hard for developing transgender people but due to lack of resources rural living transgender's not getting proper facilities.

May be this study will be helpful for the government for making the polices and enhancing their living, their acceptance from the society, good facilities and better life in ground level work.

FUTURE SUGGESTION

1. The present study has focused on the self-esteem of the transgender. Future studies may focus on

transgenders mental health.

2. This study is conducted among the transgender in West Bengal. Similar studies may be conducted in other states.
3. The present study considers only rural and urban area living transgenders. Future research may focus on different level of educated transgender's mental health with more data.

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